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CRYOGENIC IMPACT PROPERTIES OF GLASS REINFORCED POLY- DICYCLOPENTADIENE COMPOSITES

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Presentation Order

I Introduction

II Experiment Procedure

III Result and Discussion

IV Conclusion

Introduction (Background)

- Needs for composite materials
 - Reducing CO₂emmission
 - Increasing energy efficiency through 'light-weight'
 - More damage tolerant
 - Lowering cost for composite processing

< 1970 to 2018 climate change >

Introduction (Background)

- LNG CCS(Cargo Containment System) main components
 - Insulation barrier material
 - Anchoring of CCS
- Sloshing effect during LNG carrier operation
 - Fatigue accumulated of insulation system
 - Consideration of failure for fatigue accumulated
- Availability of cryogenic temperature
- Easy making complex structures

< Fatigue accumulation by sloshing effect >

< Accumulation by sloshing effect in insulation system >

Introduction (Background)

- DBTT (Ductile to Brittle Transition Temperature)
 - The temperature at which the ductile material becomes a brittle material

Experiment (Materials)

- Poly-Dicyclopentadiene monomer (endo-DCPD, 95%, Sigma-Aldrich Corp.)
- Ru-based Grubbs 2nd catalyst (2nd generation, Sigma-Aldrich Corp.)
- Decelerator (Triphenylphosphine, 99%, Sigma-Aldrich Corp.)
- Chopped Galss Fiber (450g/cm² density)

< The ring opening metathesis polymerization of DCPD with Grubbs catalyst >

< DCPD resin >

< Catalyst >

< Chopped glass fiber >

< Chopped glass fiber >

Experiment (Materials)

- Poly-Dicyclopentadiene (p-DCPD)
 - Excellent impact resistance (especially at low temperature)
 - High chemical corrosion resistance
 - Dimensional stability
- Restrictions
 - Instability in atmosphere
 - Fast curing

Property	Units	p-DCPD	Epoxy	Vinyl Ester
Tensile Strain	%	5 - 6	3 - 4	2 - 3
Tensile Modulus	Gpa	2.5	2.9	3.2
Tg	deg C	110 - 120	70 - 80	75 - 80
Water Absorption (7 days, 23°C)	%	< 1	4 - 5	2 - 4
Density	g/cc	1.04	1.15	1.14
Vol. Shrinkage	%	4 - 5	4 - 5	7 - 8

Experiment (Process)

- Processing fiber reinforced DCPD composites
 - GFRP(Glass Fiber Reinforced Plastic)
 - Throw out the bubbles and decrease porosity
 - Increase fiber volume ratio
 - Better quality test specimen than hand lay-up process

< Schematic diagram of the VARTM process >

Experiment (Specimen & machine)

- Specimen
 - International Organization for Standardization(ISO) standard test method I79-2
- Test machine
 - Charpy impact machine
 - Cryogenic chamber
 - Liquid nitrogen

< Diagram of charpy impact test >

< Cryogenic chamber and Liquid nitrogen >

Experiment (Test method)

- Impact behavior of the decelerators amount
- Charpy impact test
 - Analysis of impact absorbed energy of fiber volume fraction
(Neat, 10wt%, 20wt%, 30wt%)
 - Analysis of temperature behavior
(25, -25, -60, -110, -163)

NO.	Specimen Type	Volume fraction(wt%)	Decelator amount(%)	Temperature (°C)
1				25
2	Glass fiber/p-DPCD Reinforced Plastic	Neat	0	-20
3		10	1	-60
4		20	2	-110
5		30		-163

< Test scenario for charpy impact test >

Result and Discussion (Mechanical analysis)

- Fiber volume fraction of 20 wt%
- As the amount of the decelator increases, the impact absorbed energy decreased
- Increase decelator amount -> The lower the temperature, the less the impact property reduction

< Decelator amount of 0 wt% >

< Decelator amount of 1 wt% >

< Decelator amount of 2 wt% >

Result and Discussion (Mechanical analysis)

- Decelator amount of 2wt%
- The overall characteristics of absorbed energy versus testing temperature were observed
- p-DCPD is the absorbed energy decreased gradually as the experimental temperature decreased
- p-DCPD it can be observed that the absorbed energy decreased energy was maintained as the experimental temperature decreased
- Between the region ambient temperature and -20°C DBTT was observed

< The absorbed energy of the Neat >

< The absorbed energy of the 10wt% >

< The absorbed energy of the 20wt% >

< The absorbed energy of the 30wt% >

Conclusion

- In this study, the decelerator effect was analyzed using different amount of decelerator, which confirmed the mechanical behavior
- As the amount of the decelerator increases, the impact absorbed energy decreased
- As the fiber volume fraction increases, it is essential that the shock absorbed energy increases
- Between the region ambient temperature and -20°C DBTT was observed
- The effect of the decelerator was reduced as the temperature increased to the cryogenic temperature
- The impact energy deviation decreased with increasing cryogenic temperature

Thank you for attention